

iWRITE ENHANCEMENT MODULE AND STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING COMPETENCE IN WRITING

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effectiveness of the iWrite Enhancement Module in improving students' critical thinking competence in writing, specifically in reasoning, problem-solving, evaluating, and analyzing. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, involving pre-test and post-test assessments for both the experimental and control groups. The experimental group utilized the iWrite Enhancement Module, while the control group followed traditional classroom instruction. The module was also evaluated by experts based on content, mechanics, organization, and overall package. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and independent samples t-test. Findings revealed that the module was rated very high in effectiveness with a grand mean score of 4.28 or with a standard deviation of 0.73; With this, a significant improvement was observed in the experimental group's post-test scores t-value of 2.161 and with a p-value of 0.035, proving the module's effectiveness in fostering critical thinking competence. However, reasoning and problem-solving shown limited improvements, indicating the need for additional instructional strategies. It is recommended that higher-order thinking activities, interactive learning strategies, and extended module implementation be integrated to further enhance students' critical thinking and writing skills.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking skills, Writing Competence, iWrite Enhancement Module, Effectiveness, Lambukay IS learners*

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking competence in writing is a vital skill that enables individuals to effectively analyze, evaluate, and construct logical arguments through written communication. This ability goes beyond mere expression; it involves the careful examination of ideas, consideration of evidence, and the ability to present well-structured and reasoned arguments. In an academic context, critical thinking in writing is essential for fostering deeper understanding, improving problem-solving capabilities, and enhancing overall learning. As students navigate increasingly complex topics, developing critical thinking skills in writing equips them with the tools necessary for thoughtful analysis and effective communication, preparing them for success in both academic and professional pursuits.

In the Philippines, critical thinking is one of the favorite terms peddled by our national curriculum. It was in 1991-1999 “Education for All Philippine Plan of Action” that underlined the modern need for critical thinking to address the ills of the Philippine educational system. With this, basic education has been considered responsible for the development of critical thinking of children (Marquez, 2017). It emphasized that the learners’ formative years (5 to 8 years old) are very crucial in honing their critical thinking.

In the Department of Education (DepEd), the National Achievement Test (NAT) has been conducted to measure the academic performance of high school students. One of the areas measured by NAT is the critical thinking skills. This test helps students to become critical thinkers in the future which the K-12 curriculum expected them to become (Guevarra et, al, 2017). In short, critical thinking is not just possessing logical and cognitive skills but it is vital to students’ success in education (Lugtu, 2018).

Effective writing skills can contribute to the better critical thinking skills (Indah, 2017) of students. Hence, students need to develop their critical thinking (Marin & Halpern, 2011). The competence to express ideas on written form requires effective writing skills in developing a topic to be knowledgeable, logical, and coherent, with correct diction, and writing conventions. Therefore, problems in writing can be addressed by incorporating multiple enrichment instructions or pedagogies (Tresbe, 2020).

During the conduct of School Monitoring Evaluation and Plan Adjustment (SMEPA) of Lambukay Integrated School in Banga, South Cotabato, on December, 2023, one problem encountered was the low academic performance of students in English. It is evident in the consolidated List of Mastered and Least Learned competency in English from first quarter to fourth quarter competency are all related to writing. Also, one of the identified reasons was the returned learning activity sheets which are left unanswered by students, especially on the areas concerning writing compositions, argumentative essays, persuasive essays, and research making-related activities. This concern is also reflected in the consolidated Monitoring and Evaluation (M & E) report of teachers during their Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. This indicates that students have difficulty in putting their thoughts and ideas into words. Since writing effective essays involves focus, organization, convention, style, and logical thinking are important.

As critical thinking is one of the factors necessary for a successful learning in the 21st century, this study therefore aimed to address the problem of students in writing at Lambukay Integrated School through an alternative learning module. A learning module is referred to as a self-learning package meant to foster important skills such as time management, reading, and even critical thinking (Natividad, 2021). Research shows that if these modules are well-designed, they can significantly enhance performance among the students. It will require interaction techniques that would promote the needs of the students in putting the message across. In the end, learning modules can make a huge difference in furthering the education of the students as long as they are carefully designed for the engagement and pursuit of expertise.

Also, the researcher hoped that the result of the study can contribute to the University's vision as a leading University in advancing scholarly innovation, multi-cultural convergence, and responsive service in a borderless Region.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of iWrite Enhancement Module and Students' Critical Thinking Competence in Writing of Grade 7 students in Lambukay Integrated School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the quality of the iWrite Enhancement Module as evaluated by evaluators in terms of:

- 1.1. content;
- 1.2. mechanics;
- 1.3. organization; and,
- 1.4. over-all package?

2. What is the level of students' critical thinking competence in writing both the control and experimental groups during pre-test and post-test in terms of:

- 2.1. reasoning;
- 2.2. problem solving;
- 2.3 evaluating; and,
- 2.4 analyzing?

3. Is there a significant difference between the mean gain score of the control and experimental groups in terms of students' level of critical thinking competence in writing?

METHODOLOGY

The study used experimental research design, which is a collection of guidelines and methods designed to help researchers perform experiments utilizing two sets of variables in a scientific manner: the experimental group and the control group. The experimental group consisting of thirty (30) students who were selected randomly through a simple random sampling method, such as a lottery. This group was provided with a learning module that had been validated by a panel of validators. This was used to monitor their progress in improving their critical thinking competence in writing. The module was accompanied by direct instruction from the teacher. The control group comprised thirty (30) students who were also randomly selected through a lottery method. They received the module, but stick to traditional or conventional teaching. In addition, both the experimental and control groups were required to take a pre-test and post-test to assess their level of critical thinking competence in writing before and after the treatment. This was conducted to determine if there was any improvement in their writing skills.

This study was conducted at Lambukay Integrated School for School Year 2024-2025. The school is located at Sitio Lambukay, Barangay Lamba, Banga, South Cotabato. It is a public school that offers courses from Kinder to Senior High School. The school is a pioneering school in town which was established in the year 1969-1970. It is accommodating more than five hundred (500) students per school year and has thirty (30) teachers both in elementary and secondary. Furthermore, the locale of the study is under the supervision of the Schools' Division of South Cotabato, Region 12.

The researcher used the descriptive- evaluative design that carefully and thoroughly evaluated by English Teachers as panel of evaluators to determine the effectiveness of the research's made module in terms of its content, mechanics, organization, and over-all package. The data collected, tabulated, and interpreted to yield answers to the specific questions drawn from the statement of the problem. Thus, this research design was utilized to compare groups with pre-test and post-test data and reliability concerns, as well as measured changes as a result of the experimental treatments.

To evaluate the validity and reliability of the module, an evaluation instrument was answered by the panel of evaluators which were composed of four (4) English Master Teachers. They assessed the innovative strategy on its quality in terms of content, mechanics, organization and over-all package. A survey instrument is patterned and adapted from SKSU IMDC. A five-point Likert Scale type of questionnaire was employed in the study.

The critical thinking skills of the students which include: (1) Reasoning, (2) Problem Solving, (3) Evaluating and (4) Analyzing were checked using the rubric adapted and modified from Center for Teaching, Learning, & Technology at Washington State University (2006). It is a 5-point Likert scale that measures the proficiency level in critical thinking skills in writing.

. Mean and standard Deviation were employed to get the level of evaluation of the module in terms of content, mechanics, organization and over-all package and a t-test for independent samples was used to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the main scores of the control and experimental groups in the pre-test and post-test in terms of: (1) Descriptive Essay; (2) Expository Essay; (3) Argumentative Essay and (4) Persuasive Essay.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of the Grand Mean Ratings on the Content, Mechanics, Organization and Overall Package of the iWrite Enhancement Module

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Content	4.27	0.58	Very High Extent
Mechanics	4.37	0.81	Very High Extent
Organization	4.30	0.75	Very High Extent
Overall Package	4.17	0.79	High Extent
Grand Mean	4.28	0.73	Very High Extent

Table 2. Level of Control Group's Critical Thinking Competence in Pre-test and Post Test

	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
1. Reasoning	2.50	1.04	Beginning	3.13	1.55	Emerging
2. Problem Solving	2.50	1.20	Beginning	3.40	1.22	Emerging
3. Evaluating	2.60	1.07	Beginning	3.10	1.12	Emerging
4. Analyzing	2.50	1.04	Beginning	3.30	1.12	Emerging
Overall Mean	2.53	1.08	Beginning	3.23	1.26	Emerging

Table 3. Level of Experimental Group's Critical Thinking Competence in Pre-test and Post-test

	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
1. Reasoning	2.57	1.01	Beginning	3.77	1.33	Developing
2. Problem Solving	2.60	1.22	Beginning	4.03	1.13	Developing
3. Evaluating	2.63	1.13	Beginning	3.90	1.52	Developing
4. Analyzing	2.60	1.10	Beginning	4.03	1.03	Developing
Overall Mean	2.60	1.10	Beginning	3.93	1.26	Developing

Table 4. Results of Independent Samples t-Test on the Critical Thinking Competence in Writing of the Students between the Control Group and Experimental Group in the Post-test

Critical Thinking Skills	Control		Experimental		df	t value	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
1. Reasoning	0.63	1.97	1.20	1.73	58	1.183	0.242
2. Problem Solving	0.90	1.69	1.43	1.74	58	1.206	0.233
3. Evaluating	0.50	1.63	1.27	1.72	58	1.769	0.082
4. Analyzing	0.80	1.49	1.43	1.41	58	1.690	0.096
Overall	2.83	4.32	5.33	4.63	58	2.161	0.035*

Note: * $p < 0.05$, significant

DISCUSSION

The table 1 provides a detailed summary of the Grand Mean Ratings for an iWrite Enhancement Module, evaluated the four key indicators: Content, Mechanics, Organization, and Overall Package. According to the data, the module demonstrates consistently high performance across all measured dimensions, with a grand mean rating of 4.28 out of a possible 5.0, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.73, which indicates a relatively tight clustering of responses. Statistically, the grand mean of 4.28 represents a robust positive assessment, with the module performing exceptionally well across multiple critical dimensions. This comprehensive evaluation provides strong evidence of the module's effectiveness in supporting writing enhancement, potentially offering significant value in educational or professional writing contexts.

Table 2 showcases the level of critical thinking competence of the control group in both the pre-test and post-test across four key domains: reasoning, problem-solving, evaluating, and analyzing. The data indicate an overall improvement in critical thinking skills after the intervention, as reflected in the increase in mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test. Overall, the control group showed improvement in critical thinking competence, but the gains were modest, as the overall mean score increased from 2.53 ("Beginning") to 3.23 ("Emerging"). This suggests that while the intervention had a positive effect, it may not have been sufficient to elevate the students' critical thinking skills to higher levels of proficiency. The results imply that additional instructional strategies, extended practice, or more targeted interventions might be necessary to further enhance the students' critical thinking abilities. Moreover, the increased variability in scores suggests that differentiated instruction may be needed to support students at varying levels of competency. The findings reinforce the idea that structured learning modules can help improve students' critical thinking skills, but their design and implementation must be carefully planned to maximize effectiveness (Natividad, 2021).

Table 3 reveals a significant improvement in the experimental group's critical thinking competence across all four domains—reasoning, problem-solving, evaluating, and analyzing—following the intervention. The overall mean increased from 2.60 "Beginning" to 3.93 "Developing", indicating that the intervention effectively fostered higher-order thinking skills. Reasoning improved from 2.57 to 3.77, suggesting that students engaged in activities that strengthened their ability to construct logical arguments and assess ideas critically. Similarly, problem-solving showed the highest gain, increasing from 2.60 to 4.03, reinforcing findings by Dharma (2014) that structured learning experiences enhance students' ability to address complex challenges. This aligns with Rokhmawati et al. (2016), who found that problem-based learning strategies significantly improve students' confidence and proficiency in tackling real-world problems. The results suggest that integrating critical thinking strategies into the curriculum can significantly enhance students' ability to think logically, analyze information, and solve

problems effectively. Teachers should consider implementing similar interventions to improve students' cognitive abilities and prepare them for real-world challenges.

Table 4 publicized the results of the independent samples t-test comparing the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups in terms of critical thinking competence in writing. The overall mean gain score of the experimental group with a mean of 5.33 or with the standard deviation of 4.63 is significantly higher than that of the control group with a mean of 2.83 or with the standard deviation of 4.32, with a t-value of 2.161 and a p-value of 0.035, indicating a statistically significant difference $p < 0.05$. This suggests that the intervention had a meaningful impact on enhancing students' critical thinking competence in writing.

In general, the findings reinforce the effectiveness of structured learning interventions in enhancing overall critical thinking competence, as supported by Barrios (2017), who found that modular instruction allows students to improve at their own pace, particularly in complex cognitive tasks. However, the lack of significant differences in reasoning and problem-solving suggests that additional instructional support is necessary to strengthen these areas. Future research should explore whether extended exposure to similar interventions, more individualized instruction, or additional scaffolding strategies can lead to stronger improvements across all aspects of critical thinking.

Conclusions

The evaluation of iWrite Enhancement Module confirmed that the material highly meets the quality standards in terms of content, organization, mechanics, and over-all packaging which provides clear and well-structured information and activity making it valuable and effective learning resources for the intended learners.

The study concluded that the iWrite Enhancement Module is an effective instructional tool for improving critical thinking competence in writing, particularly in evaluating and analyzing. The significant improvement in post-test scores among the experimental group suggests that structured interventions contribute positively to students' cognitive development.

Additionally, reasoning and problem-solving skills showed limited improvement, implying that the module may require additional instructional strategies to fully enhance these aspects of critical thinking.

Overall, while the module is a valuable tool in developing writing skills, its impact on reasoning and problem-solving needs to be strengthened through further instructional improvements.

Recommendations

To further enhance the effectiveness of the iWrite Enhancement Module, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Teachers may integrate higher-order thinking activities such as problem-based learning, critical analysis tasks, and self-reflective writing exercises to strengthen reasoning and problem-solving skills.
2. Teacher may incorporate interactive learning strategies like peer evaluations, debate-based writing tasks, and real-world applications to improve students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and critique information.
3. Teacher may adapt differentiated instruction by modifying learning activities to accommodate students with varying levels of critical thinking competence and strengthen teacher facilitation through structured discussions, targeted feedback and scaffolding techniques to maximize the module's impact.
4. The future researcher may use alternative instructional approaches, such as technology-based interventions to enhance students' writing and critical thinking skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers, declares that this research is in compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in conducting the study, as well as the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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